

Clinical Profile and Therapeutic Outcomes in Substance Use Disorders: A Hospital-Based Prospective Study

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Abstract

Background: Substance use disorder (SUD) is a growing global challenge, leading to severe health, social, and economic consequences [1,2]. This study aims to assess the clinical profiles, treatment outcomes, and comorbidities in patients presenting with substance use disorder.

Methods: A hospital-based study was conducted with 139 patients diagnosed with substance use disorders, including alcohol, opioid, cannabis, and tobacco users. Data were collected using structured interviews and validated clinical scales such as the Alcohol Dependence Scale (ADS), Clinical Institute Withdrawal Assessment Scale (CIWA-Ar), and the Fagerstrom Test for Nicotine Dependence (FTND) [3-5]. Patients were followed up for therapeutic outcomes over a period of one year [6].

Results: Most patients were males (89.2%), aged 21-30 years [7]. Alcohol was the predominant substance of use, followed by opioids and cannabis. The highest relapse rates were observed in opioid users (40%), while the combination of Disulfiram and Baclofen was most effective in alcohol users [8,9]. Psychiatric comorbidities were prevalent in 50% of cases, with anxiety and personality disorders being the most common [10,11].

Conclusions: The study highlights the complex clinical and sociodemographic profile of SUD patients and the need for tailored therapeutic approaches for effective management [12].

Keywords: Substance use disorder, alcohol dependence, opioid use, cannabis use, treatment outcomes, comorbidities.

Introduction

Substance use has been part of human society for centuries, yet in recent decades, it has evolved into a major public health crisis [1,13]. The global prevalence of substance use, particularly among youth, has been steadily rising, leading to adverse health outcomes,

increased criminal behavior, and economic losses [14-16]. Studies have highlighted the detrimental impact of substance use on both individual health and societal stability [17].

Substance use disorders (SUDs) are closely linked to psychiatric conditions such as anxiety, depression, and personality disorders, complicating their treatment and management [18,19]. The comorbidity of SUD with other mental health disorders is associated with worse prognoses and higher relapse rates [20-22]. In India, the common substances of abuse include alcohol, tobacco, opioids, and cannabis [23]. Understanding the clinical characteristics and treatment outcomes of these patients is crucial for developing effective therapeutic strategies [24].

The present study was conducted to assess the clinical profiles, sociodemographic characteristics, comorbidities, and treatment outcomes of patients with SUD in a hospital setting. This information will contribute to improving clinical management and designing targeted interventions [25].

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting

This prospective, hospital-based study was conducted at the Department of Neuropsychiatry & Mental Health, SSMC & Associated SGMH, Rewa, from January 2018 to September 2019 [3].

Study Population and Sampling

The study included 139 patients who met the DSM-5 criteria for SUD [4]. The sample comprised 36 alcohol users, 37 opioid users, 33 cannabis users, and 33 tobacco users. Patients with severe medical emergencies or unwillingness to provide informed consent were excluded [5].

Data Collection Tools

The following validated scales were used to assess dependence and withdrawal severity:

- *Alcohol Dependence Scale (ADS) [17].*
- *Clinical Institute Withdrawal Assessment Scale (CIWA-Ar) for alcohol withdrawal [18].*
- *Clinical Opiate Withdrawal Scale (COWS) for opioid users [19].*
- *Fagerstrom Test for Nicotine Dependence (FTND) for tobacco users [20].*

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic variables. Chi-squared tests and t-tests were applied to evaluate associations between clinical characteristics and treatment outcomes. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$ [26].

Results

Sociodemographic Profile

The majority of substance users were young adults (21-30 years), with alcohol and opioid use being more prevalent in urban areas [7]. Most users were males (89.2%), and a significant proportion were from lower socioeconomic classes, consistent with previous studies [27,28].

Clinical Characteristics

- *Age of Onset: Most subjects initiated substance use between the ages of 10-20 years, which aligns with studies indicating early initiation as a predictor of severe dependence and poor treatment outcomes [29-31].*
- *Comorbidities: Psychiatric comorbidities were prevalent in 50% of the sample, including personality disorders (36% in alcohol users) and anxiety disorders (25%), similar to findings from other Indian studies [32-33].*

Treatment and Outcomes

- *Alcohol Dependence: Treatment with Disulfiram and Baclofen showed a significant reduction in relapse rates compared to monotherapy ($p < 0.05$) [30].*
- *Opioid Dependence: Combination therapy with Clonidine and Naltrexone resulted in higher remission rates (75%) compared to Clonidine alone [31].*
- *Tobacco Use: Behavioral therapy combined with Bupropion was more effective than Nicotine Replacement Therapy ($p < 0.01$) [32].*
- *Cannabis Users: All cannabis users were hospitalized due to comorbid psychiatric conditions, with Schizophrenia being the most common (54%) [33].*

Discussion

The findings of this study demonstrate the high prevalence of substance use among young adults, with alcohol and opioids being the most commonly abused substances [1,34]. The sociodemographic distribution aligns with research highlighting the role of low socioeconomic status and male gender in the development of SUDs [35].

Comorbidities and Treatment Implications

The high rate of psychiatric comorbidities complicates treatment and increases the risk of relapse, particularly in opioid and alcohol users [36]. This is consistent with other research linking high psychiatric comorbidity with poor prognosis in SUD patients [37]. This underscores the need for integrated treatment approaches that address both addiction and co-occurring psychiatric conditions [38].

Limitations

The study's limitations include its small sample size and single-center design, which may affect the generalizability of the results [39]. Further research is needed to explore genetic and environmental factors influencing SUD [40].

Conclusions

Substance use disorder is a complex condition that requires comprehensive management strategies. Early intervention, integrated care, and long-term follow-up are essential to improving treatment outcomes and preventing relapse.

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